

Free-standing electrochemically coated MoS_x based 3D-printed nanocarbon electrode for solid-state supercapacitor application†

Cite this: DOI: 10.1039/d0nr06479c

 Kalyan Ghosh ^{*a,b,c,d}

The 3D-printing technology offers an innovative approach to develop energy storage devices because of its ability to create facile and low cost customized electrodes for modern electronics. Among the recently explored 2D nanomaterials beyond graphene, molybdenum sulfide has been found as a promising material for electrochemical energy storage devices. In this study, a nanocarbon-based conductive filament was 3D-printed and then activated by solvent treatment followed by electrodeposition of MoS_x on the printed nano-carbon electrode's surface. The conductive nanocarbon fibers allow a coaxial deposition of a thin MoS_x layer. The MoS_x layer contributes to pseudocapacitive charge storage mechanisms to obtain higher capacitances. In a three-electrode test system with 1 M H₂SO₄ as electrolyte, the MoS_x coated 3D-printed electrode (MoS_x@3D-PE) electrode shows a capacitance of 27 mF cm⁻² at the scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹, and a capacitance of 11.6 mF cm⁻² at the current density of 0.13 mA cm⁻². Extending to solid-state supercapacitor (SS-SC), the cells were fabricated using the MoS_x@3D-PE with different designs and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)/H₂SO₄ as gel electrolyte. An interdigital-shaped SS-SC provided a specific capacitance of 4.15 mF cm⁻² at a current density of 0.05 mA cm⁻². Moreover, it showed a stable cycle life where 10% capacitance retention was found after 10 000 cycles. Briefly, this study reports the integration of 3D-printing and room-temperature electrodeposition techniques allowing a simple way of fabricating customized free-standing 3D-electrodes for use in SC applications.

Received 8th September 2020.

Accepted 3rd March 2021

DOI: 10.1039/d0nr06479c

rsc.li/nanoscale

Introduction

Recently, the increasing number of modern electronics from different segments such as mobiles, laptops, health care monitoring devices, flexible displays, and others increases the demand for energy storage devices.^{1,2} Therefore, it has become a primary prerequisite to develop facile, customized and inexpensive energy storage devices.³ Supercapacitors (SCs) are becoming increasingly popular as an energy storage device because of their moderate energy density, high power density, and superior cycle life compared to batteries.^{4–6} Besides, the future energy storage devices are foreseen to be lightweight,

flexible, wearable, and customizable. For these criteria, additive manufacturing or 3D-printing leads a pivotal role to revolutionize the research in energy storage.³ 3D-printing technique offers rapid prototyping and large scale industrial manufacturing in a preferred shape. Through 3D-printing, diverse materials can be fabricated in complex 3D geometries by varying the feeding or precursor material to achieve the desired chemical, physical and electronic properties.^{7,8}

In a conventional SC,^{9,10} the positive and negative electrodes, and the separator are rolled or stacked in a planar 2D arrangement.^{9,10} The limitation of this configuration is that the electrolyte ions diffuse in one dimension between the two electrodes which then limits the electrochemical performances.¹¹ Through the 3D-printing technique, a topological optimization of batteries and SCs has been realized.⁸ For SC, the major components such as positive and negative electrodes, current collectors, and separators can be customized to a desired 3D shape and size to fit into complex 3D electronics devices as power sources.^{7,12} The 3D electrode has a higher amount of electrochemically active sites in the same footprint area which facilitates 2D or 3D diffusion of electrolyte ions.⁸ Recently, several research groups followed different 3D-printing approaches for the fabrication of 3D electrodes for SC

^aFuture Energy and Innovation Laboratory, Central European Institute of Technology, Brno University of Technology, Purkyňova 123, 61200 Brno, Czech Republic.

 E-mail: pumera.research@gmail.com
^bDepartment of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Mendel University in Brno, Zemedelska 1, 613 00 Brno, Czech Republic

^cDepartment of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, Yonsei University, 50 Yonsei-ro, Seodaemun-guSeoul 03722, Korea

^dDepartment of Medical Research, China Medical University Hospital, China Medical University, No. 91 Hsueh-Shih Road, Taichung 40402, Taiwan

†Electronic supplementary information (ESI) available. See DOI: 10.1039/d0nr06479c

applications.^{7,8,12–16} Among the different 3D-printing techniques, fused deposition modeling (FDM) was found to be a promising technique for the fabrication of SCs due to their low cost and facile fabrication style. In FDM technique, a filament is extruded through a nozzle and deposited layer-by-layer to obtain a 3D structure.^{8,17} The filament commonly employed in FDM printing is made of thermoplastic materials such as polylactic acid (PLA) or acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene (ABS) polymers. Pioneer work was reported by Foster *et al.* to develop electrodes using a commercial graphene/PLA filament as the material source which consists of 8 wt% of graphene and 92 wt% of PLA, which shows a specific capacitance of 15.8 mA h g⁻¹.¹⁴ Recently, several studies have been carried out by our group to develop electrodes using commercial conductive graphene/PLA filament for different electrochemical and sensing applications.^{18–26} To conform the printing requirement, the amount of active material in the filament has to be limited, which is insufficient for high electrochemical performance. However, the facile 3D-printing of such conductive filament opens up new space for rapid prototyping of electrode materials. External mass loading of electrochemically active material on the printed electrode surface could expedite the wide use of FDM technique for energy storage device fabrication. Foo *et al.* deposited electrochemical active polypyrrole (PPy) on electrode surface to obtain higher electrochemical performance.²⁷ This approach provides a guideline to deposit numerous electroactive capacitive materials such as metal oxides and transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) on the printed electrode surface for several electrochemical applications. Lately, 2D transition metal dichalcogenide, MoS₂ has become a promising material in the field of energy storage devices due to their unique electronic and structural properties.^{28,29} In a single layer of MoS₂, one Mo atom is sandwiched by two sulfur atoms, and in a multilayer MoS₂, the layers are stacked by weak van der Waal forces which allow easy ions intercalation. As the Mo atom possesses a wide range of oxidation states from +2 to +6, it shows a promising pseudocapacitive behavior. A theoretical capacitance of MoS₂ was found to be 1000 F g⁻¹.^{29,30} So far, chemical vapor deposition (CVD),^{31,32} hydrothermal synthesis,^{33,34} liquid phase exfoliation process,^{35,36} intercalation-exfoliation methods,^{37,38} and electrodeposition^{39–41} have been employed to synthesize MoS₂ in bulk quantities. Electrodeposition is found to be a simpler and cost-effective approach than CVD and other allied methods that involve complex routes and expensive vacuum technologies. Moreover, electrodeposition rapidly produces *nano*-to-micrometer thick films and provides good control over the film thickness as compared to the exfoliation and solution phase methods. The room-temperature electrodeposition does not typically grow crystalline or polycrystalline material without post-processing. Nevertheless, amorphous coating of MoS₂ could be an outstanding pseudocapacitive material for high-performance SC applications. As the charge storage mechanism of a SC is mostly limited to the surface of the material, a thin MoS₂ coating on the 3D-printed electrode could enhance the pseudocapacitance elevating the overall capacitive performance.

Thus, in this study, we report low cost and scalable 3D-printing of a conductive nanocarbon/PLA filament followed by room-temperature electrodeposition of MoS_x layer on the activated 3D-printed electrode. The MoS_x coated 3D-printed electrode (MoS_x@3D-PE) acts as a free-standing electrode without the requirement of any external current collector. This process eliminates an additional component of a SC to achieve low weight-to-volume ratio. The electrodeposition process produces a thin coaxial layer of MoS_x on the activated 3D-printed nanocarbon fibers which induces pseudocapacitive reactions to enhance the overall performance of the 3D electrode. In addition, solid-state supercapacitors (SS-SCs) were fabricated using different customized shaped MoS_x@3D-PEs. The solid-state electrolyte prevents possible leakage of electrolyte and ensures safe use of SS-SC in the electronics devices. In short, this work enlightens a room-temperature deposition of MoS_x on the customized free-standing 3D-printed electrodes for SS-SC applications.

Experimental

Materials

The commercial graphene/polylactic acid (PLA) filament (BlackMagic3D®) was procured from Graphene Laboratories Inc., New York USA. The ammonium tetrathiomolybdate (NH₄MoS₄) and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Germany. The potassium chloride (KCl), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF), and sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) were procured from Penta, Czech Republic. All chemicals were of analytical grade. All solutions were prepared in deionized (DI) water (resistivity >18 MΩ cm).

Fabrication of 3D-printed nanocarbon electrodes

Three different shapes of electrodes (cylindrical shape with an arm, interdigital- and CEITEC-shape) were designed using the Autodesk Fusion Lab 360 software as depicted in Fig. S1, ESI.† The designed electrodes were 3D-printed employing the commercial graphene/PLA filament using a Prusa 3D Printer (Prusa i3 MK3S, Czech Republic), where the nozzle temperature was kept at 220 °C with the bed temperature of 60 °C, 15% infill and 0.15 mm of layer height. The as-printed electrodes were activated by solvent treatment through immersing in DMF for 4 hours followed by washing with ethanol and DI water to remove the dissolved PLA from the 3D-printed electrodes and then dried in an electric oven for 5 hours at 60 °C. The activated 3D-printed electrodes are denoted as 3D-PE in the following sections. A schematic presentation of the 3D-printing and solvent activation process is shown in Fig. 1a and b, respectively.

Preparation of MoS_x coated 3D-printed electrodes

The MoS_x layer was coated on the 3D-PEs surface by an electrodeposition technique following a modified version of our previous work.^{18,42} The electrodeposition *via* cyclic voltammetry (CV) scan was carried out in a three-electrode test setup using the glassy carbon (GC, 3 mm diameter) or free-standing 3D-PE

Fig. 1 Schematic presentation of (a) 3D-printing of electrodes, (b) solvent activation of 3D-printed electrodes, (c) before and (d) after the electro-deposition, and (e) fabrication of solid-state supercapacitor cells as an energy source application.

as working electrode, Pt wire as counter electrode and Ag/AgCl (1 M KCl) as a reference electrode in 5 mM ammonium tetrathiomolybdate ((NH₄)₂MoS₄) with 0.1 M KCl electrolyte. A photograph of the electrodeposition setup is depicted in Fig. S2.† The CV was measured by a potentiostat (Metrohm Autolab, PGSTAT 204, Netherlands) at the scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹ by varying the potential window between -1.5 to +0.8 V for 5 to 100 CV cycles. The optimal potential window and number of CV cycles were determined based on the electrochemical capacitive performance. After electrodeposition, the MoS_x coated 3D-printed electrodes (MoS_x@3D-PE) were gently rinsed with deionized water to remove the free and loosely bound ions from the electrode and dried at ambient temperature. The electrodes were then stored for further characterization and electrochemical analysis purposes. A schematic presentation of the MoS_x deposition on the 3D-PEs is shown in Fig. 1c and d.

Fabrication of solid-state supercapacitor cell

The solid-state supercapacitor (SS-SC) cell was fabricated by simply assembling two identical electrodes utilizing the PVA/H₂SO₄ gel electrolyte. The active areas of the electrodes were dipped in H₂SO₄ for 2 hours and then placed in an open box followed by encapsulation with the gel electrolyte as shown in Fig. S3.† The gel electrolyte plays a dual role, as an electrolyte as

well as a separator between the two electrodes, and thus eliminates the use of external separator. The PVA/H₂SO₄ gel electrolyte was prepared following a modified procedure as mentioned in the literature.⁴³ Briefly, 4 g of PVA was dissolved in 40 mL H₂O by heating it at 90 °C until the solution becomes clear, and then 4 g (2.27 mL) of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added dropwise. The solution was then cooled to room temperature and stored in a glass vial. The gel was later used to fabricate the SS-SCs.

Materials characterization

A series of materials characterization was performed on blank 3D-PE and 20 cycles MoS_x@3D-PE to confirm the deposited material. The surface morphology was characterized using the scanning electron microscope (SEM, FEI VERIOS 460L). The chemical composition and elemental mapping were carried out using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) detector (EDAX SDD Octane Super) attached along with the SEM. Moreover, to determine the chemical composition and bonding environment, the X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, Kratos AXIS Supra) was carried out with a monochromatic Al Kα (1486.7 eV) excitation source. Raman spectroscopy measurement was conducted using WITec alpha300R with an excitation wavelength of 532 nm and a laser power of 25 mW. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were measured using an

X-ray diffractometer (Rigaku SmartLab 3 kW) setting up Bragg Brentano geometry using Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm). The diffractometer was operated at a current of 30 mA and a voltage of 40 kV. The electrochemical analyses comprising of cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) were carried out by the same potentiostat mentioned above. The cylindrical-shaped electrode with an arm and SS-SC cell can withstand freely without any external support for electrochemical measurements as shown in Fig. S4.† The MoS $_x$ coated active area considered during electrochemical measurements for all the printed electrodes are shown in Fig. S5.† The specific capacitances from CV and GCD studies, energy density, and power density were calculated following eqn (S1)–(S4) in the ESI.†

Results and discussion

The electrochemical deposition of MoS $_x$ by CV technique was optimized *via* two critical parameters, namely by varying the potential window and the number of CV cycles. Different potential windows of -1.3 to -0.2 V, -1.3 to 0 V, -1.3 to $+0.2$ V, -1.3 to $+0.4$ V, -1.3 to $+0.6$ V, -1.3 to $+0.8$ V, -1.5 to $+0.6$ V and -1.1 to $+0.6$ V were applied for 10 CV cycles on GC electrode. The corresponding cyclic voltammograms are depicted in Fig. 2a. The cyclic voltammogram for the deposition carried out at -1.3 to 0 V (light blue) shows a well-defined oxidative peak at -0.2 V and the corresponding reduction peak at -0.8 V. Extending the potential limit towards anodic side to $+0.8$ V (black), another pair of oxidative and reductive peaks were detected at $+0.5$ and -1.1 V, respectively. Hence, two redox pairs were observed for -1.3 to $+0.6$ V (red). Meanwhile, when the cathodic potential limit was shifted to -1.5 V (olive green), hydrogen evolution reaction was observed. Although, increasing of the anodic limit from $+0.6$ V (red) to $+0.8$ V (black) produced similar anodic signals, the corresponding cathodic signal shifted from -0.8 V towards more negative potential of -1.0 V. Further, to find out the highest capacitive performance from all the MoS $_x$ coated glassy carbon electrode (MoS $_x$ @GC) the CV capacitance analysis were carried out in 1 M H $_2$ SO $_4$ electrolyte. The individual CV curves are included in Fig. S6† for reference. The obtained specific capacitances with respect to the potential windows shown in Fig. 2b reveals that the MoS $_x$ deposited by -1.3 to $+0.6$ V provides the highest capacitive performance.

We proceeded with this potential range for the electrodeposition on 3D-printed electrode (3D-PE) with different number of cycles for 5, 10, 20, 25, 50, and 100. A 3D-PE with 20 cycles of CV deposition was used for morphological and chemical composition analyses. The 3D-PE after DMF activation retain its original shape, although the PLA polymer matrix is partially removed from the surface leaving the nanocarbon fibers exposed as observed from the SEM micrographs in Fig. 3a and b. The removal of PLA was also evident from the mass loss of $\sim 20\%$ after DMF treatment. From Fig. 3b, it is found that the diameters of the nanocarbon fibers are about 80 – 150 nm and a length in the range of few micrometers. After

Fig. 2 (a) Cyclic voltammograms for MoS $_x$ deposition on the glassy carbon electrode at different potential windows and (b) specific capacitances at different potential windows.

the electrodeposition, a uniform coating was observed on the surface of each nanocarbon fiber seeming like a coaxial structure at MoS $_x$ @3D-PE as observed in Fig. 3c. The diameters of the MoS $_x$ coated coaxial fibers were found to be 190 – 250 nm. This expresses that ~ 50 nm of MoS $_x$ layer formed through the electrodeposition method. A mass deposition of MoS $_x$ on 3D-PE of ~ 0.36 mg cm $^{-2}$ was calculated through gravimetric measurement. The energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis was carried out to confirm the elemental composition of the de-

Fig. 3 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of (a) 3D-printed electrode: inset-optical image (b) solvent activated 3D-printed electrode: inset optical image and (c) MoS_x coated 3D-printed electrode (MoS_x@3D-PE); (d) energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy mapping area, (e) Mo L and (f) S K elemental mapping of MoS_x@3D-PE.

posited MoS_x. The EDX analysis reports the atomic percentage of C, O, Mo, and S are 44.68, 32.76, 5.05, and 14.18%, respectively, as shown in Fig. S7.† The atomic percentage ratio of Mo and S was found to be 1 : 2.8. Besides, electrolyte during the electrodeposition process traces amount of K, Cl, and Ti were found in the MoS_x@3D-PE. The presence of K and Cl is originated from the KCl used as supporting. The presence of Ti is sourced from the inherent metal impurity in the filament.^{14,23,24} Certainly, the Mo L and S K mapping endorse the presence of coaxial deposition of MoS_x onto the nanocarbon fibers as observed from Fig. 3e and f, respectively.

Further, to confirm the bonding environment and chemical composition, high-resolution X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurement was carried out for MoS_x@3D-PE as shown in Fig. 4. The survey spectrum confirms the presence of O 1s, Mo 3p, C 1s, Mo 3d, and S 2p as depicted in Fig. 4a. The surface atomic percentages of C, O, Mo, and S were calculated to be 44.20, 14.20, 12.38, and 29.38%, respectively. The presence of C and O are originated from the surface functional groups of graphitic nanocarbon and remaining PLA. The ratio of the atomic percentage of Mo 3d and S 2s was calculated to be 1 : 2.38. To further analyze the bonding states of Mo, deconvolution of Mo 3d spectrum was carried out, which displays two more intense peaks located at 229.69 and 232.84 eV correspond to Mo⁴⁺ 3d_{5/2} and Mo⁴⁺ 3d_{3/2}, respectively keeping a spin-orbit peak separation of 3.15 eV (Fig. 4b). Moreover, two lower peaks positioned at 231.50 and 234.65 eV can be attributed to Mo⁶⁺ 3d_{5/2} and Mo⁶⁺ 3d_{3/2}, respectively.⁴⁴ The atomic percentage ratio of Mo⁴⁺ to Mo⁶⁺ is calculated to be 1.75 : 1. Moreover, the obvious peak positioned at 226.79 eV corresponds to the S 2s.⁴⁴

The deconvolution spectrum of S 2p is depicted in Fig. 4c. The peaks appeared at 162.20 and 163.36 eV correspond to the S²⁻ 2p_{3/2} and S²⁻ 2p_{1/2}, respectively acquainting a spin-orbit peak separation of 1.16 eV. Moreover, two other peaks located at 163.64 and 164.80 eV can be ascribed to the bridging S₂²⁻ bonding state of S₃ ligand.⁴⁵ The observed atomic ratio of Mo and S (1 : 2.38), and oxidation states of Mo (Mo⁴⁺ and Mo⁶⁺) confirm the formation of MoS₂ and MoS₃. The ratio of MoS₂/MoS₃ is expected to be 1.75 : 1 as spotted from the atomic percentage of Mo⁴⁺ and Mo⁶⁺.

The mixed phases of MoS₂ and MoS₃ can be ascribed to the reduction and oxidation processes involved in the CV potential sweep from -1.3 to +0.6 V for the electrochemical deposition of MoS_x.⁴² The corresponding cyclic voltammograms for first 3 cycles are depicted in Fig. S8† The MoS₂ is formed by the reduction of precursors [MoS₄]²⁻ at the potential of -0.8 V, where the [MoS₄]²⁻ is reduced to MoS₂ by changing the oxidation state of Mo from +6 to +4. The reduction reaction can be stated by eqn (1).^{40,41}

On the other hand, in the anodic process, the oxidation peak at -0.2 V is responsible to the formation of MoS₃. In this process, the oxidation of a sulfide ligand occurred followed by an intramolecular electron transfer to the Mo and then the loss of S to form MoS₃ which can be stated by eqn (2).^{46,47}

Thus, both MoS₂ and MoS₃ phases were deposited in the chosen potential window.

Fig. 4 High-resolution X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy of MoS_x coated 3D-printed electrode (a) survey spectra: table in the inset shows the atomic percentages of constituent elements, deconvolution spectra of (b) Mo 3d and (c) S 2p.

The XRD analysis was carried out for 3D-PE and $\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$ as shown in Fig. 5a. It was found that the peaks obtained from the 3D-PE are well-matched with the $\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$, and no other obvious peaks appeared from

Fig. 5 (a) X-ray diffraction pattern and (b) Raman spectroscopy analysis of 3D-PE and MoS_x coated 3D-printed electrode ($\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$).

MoS_x coating which apparently revealed that the electrodeposited MoS_x is of amorphous nature.^{40,48} The major peaks appeared at 14.7, 16.6, 18.9, and 22.2° are corresponding to the diffraction pattern from pure PLA⁴⁸ and the peak located at 26.3° (pointed by an arrow) is corresponding to the diffraction from graphitic-like carbon.^{49,50}

To further confirm the chemical structure, defects, and crystallinity of the MoS_x phase, Raman spectroscopy was carried out for the 3D-PE and $\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$ in the spectral range 100–3600 cm^{-1} as depicted in Fig. 5b. It has been found that the Raman spectrum of $\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$ coincides well with the 3D-PE, which is in line with XRD analysis confirming again the amorphous phase of the MoS_x layer. The peaks appeared at 157, 400, and 609 cm^{-1} (pointed as * in Fig. 5b) for both the 3D-PE and $\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$ can be attributed to the TiO_2 ^{51,52} which is present in the filament as inherent impurity.^{24,53} Additionally, two other intense peaks appeared at 1340 and 1565 cm^{-1} correspond to the well-known D-band and G-band, respectively of graphene-like structures.⁵⁴ The

intensity ratio (I_D/I_G) for the 3D-PE and MoS_x@3D-PE are calculated to be 0.49 and 0.55, respectively which once again confirm the presence of defects and functional groups in the graphene-like nanocarbon fibers.⁵⁴ Moreover, the peak located at 2680 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to the 2D peak of graphitic carbon. For MoS_x@3D-PE, the decrease of peak intensity for the carbon related peaks as compared to the 3D-PE evidenced the presence of coating on the nanocarbon fibers.

The electrochemical performance of the MoS_x@3D-PEs for different deposition cycles are evaluated by CV study in 1 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte as shown in Fig. 6a. The corresponding specific capacitances with different deposition cycles at the scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹ are depicted in Fig. 6b. It is observed that the current-voltage area which is related to stored charge is increased with the increase of deposition cycles till 20–25 cycles, and then decreased with further increase of the deposition cycles to 50 and 100 cycles. From Fig. 6b, it can be confirmed that a maximum specific capacitance was obtained at 25 cycles of deposition. Moreover, the shape of the CV curves at higher deposition cycles account for low current intensities with the increase of inherent resistivity at the electrode. This can be ascribed to the deposition of thicker amount of MoS_x on the conductive 3D-PE surface with higher deposition cycles inhibit the charge transfer from the MoS_x@3D-PE/electrolyte interface to the core 3D-PE. Based on the capacitive performance of the MoS_x@3D-PEs for different deposition cycles, the 25 CV cycles was selected for the in-depth electrochemical analysis of the MoS_x@3D-PEs.

To study the electrochemical behavior of the cylindrical-shaped MoS_x@3D-PE, CV and GCD measurements were carried out in the three-electrode test setup in 1 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte. The MoS_x@3D-PE shows free-standing behavior where no external current collector is required for electrochemical measurement. The CV was carried out over a wide range of scan rates from 5–100 mV s⁻¹ in the potential window of 0–0.8 V as shown in Fig. 7a. The shape of the CV curves displays a distorted rectangular pattern suggesting the pseudocapacitive behavior by the MoS_x in the acidic medium. With increasing the scan rates, the anodic and cathodic peaks current increase in a proportional manner, which indicates a very good rate capability of the electrode. The CV study of the blank 3D-PE at the scan rates of 10–300 mV s⁻¹ is presented in Fig. S9.† The bare electrode shows good current-potential response where an increase of scan rate increases the current density. However, the obtained current intensity is found to be low. Apparently, the MoS_x coating dramatically increases the current density as observed by comparing the CV studies of the 3D-PE and MoS_x@3D-PE. The specific capacitances of the 3D-PE and MoS_x@3D-PE at the scan rates of 10–100 mV s⁻¹ are compared in Fig. 7b. It was found that the specific capacitance increased ~10 times with the MoS_x coating. This higher capacitance can be attributed to the fast surface redox reaction by the thin MoS_x layer. The MoS_x stores charge by changing the valence state of Mo ion during electrode polarization and contributes an additional pseudocapacitance. The surface adsorption/desorption and intercalation/de-intercalation of

Fig. 6 (a) Cyclic voltammtery study of MoS_x coated 3D-PE at different deposition cycles, and (b) the variation of specific capacitances with deposition cycles.

protons by MoS_x can be described by eqn (3) and (4), respectively.^{55,56}

Fig. 7 (a) Cyclic voltammetry (CV) study at different scan rates, (b) specific capacitance comparison with blank 3D-PE, (c) $\log(\text{peak current density, mA cm}^{-2})$ vs. $\log(\text{scan rates, mV s}^{-1})$ and linear fitting to determine b value for anodic peaks, (d) separation of the stored charge into capacitive and intercalative contribution at scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} , (e) charge storage separation for 25, 50, 75 and 100 mV s^{-1} and (f) galvanostatic charge–discharge study at different current densities of the cylindrical-shaped 25 cycles MoS_x coated 3D-printed electrode ($\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$) in 1 M H_2SO_4 electrolyte.

evaluating the kinetics of the redox reaction, which can be stated by eqn (5).

$$i = av^b \quad (5)$$

Further, to elucidate the surface redox reaction, we followed the approach shown by Augustyn and co-workers⁵⁷ through

where, i is peak current, ν is scan rate, and a and b are variant. The value b equals to 1 represents surface-controlled capacitive mechanism whereas the value of b equals to 0.5 represents diffusion-controlled battery-like pseudocapacitive reaction.^{57–59}

The eqn (5) can be rearranged into eqn (6) as.

$$\log i = \log a + b \log \nu \quad (6)$$

The b value was found to be 0.74 by plotting $\log i$ against $\log \nu$ for the scan rates from 10 to 100 mV s^{-1} as depicted in Fig. 7c. This b value indicates that the kinetics follows both surface-controlled and diffusion controlled mechanism. Additionally, the charge storage by the $\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$ can be divided into the charge contributed by faradic contribution *i.e.* diffusion controlled/intercalation process and by the non-faradic contribution *i.e.* electrochemical double-layer (EDL) formation following the approach by Dunn and co-workers.⁶⁰ The current response (i) at a fixed potential (V) can be divided into the capacitive process ($k_1\nu$) and battery-like diffusion-controlled process ($k_2\nu^{1/2}$) following eqn (7).

$$i(V) = k_1\nu + k_2\nu^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

where, ν is scan rate. k_1 and k_2 are the constants. The eqn (7) can be rearranged into eqn (8).

$$i(V)/\nu^{1/2} = k_1 \nu^{1/2} + k_2 \quad (8)$$

The k_1 and k_2 values can be calculated by plotting $i(V)/\nu^{1/2}$ versus $\nu^{1/2}$ varying the scan rates.⁶¹ Thus from eqn (7), $k_1\nu$ and $k_2\nu^{1/2}$ can be determined. Fig. 7d displays the separation of charge storing contriving by different mechanism, where pink shaded area presents the charge stored by double-layer mechanism and the blue shaded area represents the charge storing through pseudocapacitive intercalation mechanism. It has been found that 31% of total capacitance was contributed by pseudocapacitive charge storage process at the scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} . Fig. 7e shows the separation of capacitive contribution to the pseudocapacitive contribution at different scan rates. It was found that higher scan rate displays higher capacitive contribution which is due to the faster transfer of ions into the electrodes. It is noteworthy to mention that the Ti-based impurities observed by EDX did not actively contribute to the capacitance. In this study, as the surface of the 3D-printed electrode is covered by the MoS_x layers of ~ 50 nm, capacitive contribution from the bulk Ti impurity was suppressed. The oxidation and reduction peaks ascribed to the Ti-based impurity in the thermally activated 3D-printed electrode produced by the same filament in our previous study⁵³ were absent in the present study. Here, the charge storage is solely contributed by $\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$ and is not influenced by the inherent Ti impurity.

Further, the GCD study of the $\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$ was carried out at different current densities within the same potential window of 0–0.8 V as shown in Fig. 7f. The charge–discharge patterns show symmetrical behavior, which corroborates with the result obtained in the CV study. The electrode shows the specific capacitances of 13.19, 7.73, 6.82, 6.36, and 5.68 mF cm^{-2} at the constant current densities of 0.18, 0.36, 0.55, 0.73

and 0.91 mA cm^{-2} , respectively. It was found that the capacitance is increasing with decreasing the current density. This can be attributed to the slower ion insertion-desertion process at lower current density, which facilitates the access of higher active area of the $\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$ and increases the capacitance. Conversely, at higher current density, the diffusion and migration of electrolytes ions are limited. Based on the promising result as obtained by the free-standing cylindrical-shaped $\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$, we fabricated a free-standing interdigital-shaped SS-SC cell using two identical $\text{MoS}_x@3\text{D-PE}$ s with PVA/ H_2SO_4 gel electrolyte as reported in the Experimental section. A photograph of the interdigital-shaped SS-SC is shown in Fig. 8a. It is significant to mention here that no external current collector was used to fabricate the SC cell. To evaluate the electrochemical performance of the SS-SC cell, CV, GCD, EIS, and long term cyclic stability studies were performed. The CV plots at different scan rates from 0–0.6 V are depicted in Fig. 8b. It is seen that the specific currents increase with increasing the scan rates from 10 to 500 mV s^{-1} which illustrate the high rate capability of the solid-state cell. The GCD study at different current densities is shown in Fig. 8c. The GCD profile shows symmetrical charge–discharge profile. The discharge profile shows a IR drop of 0.04 V at the current density of 0.05 mA cm^{-2} . The SS-SC shows the specific capacitances of 4.15, 3.61, 3.25 and 3.16 mF cm^{-2} at the current densities of 0.05, 0.11, 0.22 and 0.27 mA cm^{-2} , respectively.

The EIS study was carried out for the SS-SC to evaluate the impedance behavior of the electrode in the frequency range of 100 kHz to 0.1 Hz applying an alternating current amplitude of 10 mV. The Nyquist plot with the simulated data is depicted in Fig. 8d. The plot shows a semicircle at the high-frequency region followed by an inclined line in the low-frequency region. The simulated circuit model is displayed in Fig. 8e. The circuit model takes into account the charge storage mechanisms occurring at the electrode–electrolyte interface of a conductor electrode with a coating layer.^{62,63} In the circuit model, the resistive element R_s includes intrinsic resistance of the electrode, interfacial resistance between electrodes and electrolyte, and ionic resistance of the electrolyte. The intercept at Z' -axis in high-frequency region signifies the R_s value. The R_p represents the resistance through-pores of the coated layer.⁶³ The parameter W_d is Warburg resistance which is a measure of ionic diffusion/transport from the electrolyte to the surface of the electrode.⁶⁴ The slope of the straight line in the low-frequency region states the W_d . The CPE (Y_0, S^n) is a constant phase element which represents a Warburg impedance with diffusional character, that elucidates the deviation of a SC cell from the ideal capacitive behavior. The parameter R_{ct} represents the charge transfer resistance which is originated from the charge transfer reaction at the electrode–electrolyte interface, which is also known as Faradic resistance. The diameter of the semicircle quantifies the R_{ct} . The CPE_2/R_{ct} represents the faradic process involved at the electrode–electrolyte interface through the pores of the coated layer.⁶³ In a real SC, the presence of CPE is due to several reasons such as charge transfer at the electrode, non-uniform reaction sites distribution, or some physical defects like the thickness of the elec-

Fig. 8 (a) Photograph, (b) cyclic voltammetry, (c) galvanostatic charge-discharge, (d) Nyquist plot, (e) simulated circuit model for impedance study (f) Bode plot (g) Ragone plot and (h) cyclic stability study for 10 000 cycles of the free-standing interdigital-shape SS-SC.

trode and other related factors. The impedance (Z) is related to CPE (Y_0) by the eqn (9):⁶⁵

$$Z = (Y_0 j \omega)^{-n} \quad (9)$$

where, ω is the angular frequency. The power factor n diverges as $0 < n < 1$. The n value closer to 1 indicates ideal

EDL-type SC behavior. The values of the circuit parameters are shown in Table 1. The series resistance R_s was found to be of 49 Ω , which is because of the high solution resistance from PVA/H₂SO₄ gel electrolyte. The R_{ct} was found to be 91.9 Ω . The equivalent circuit reveals that the value of n_1 is 0.81. This value suggests that the charge-discharge behavior of the SS-SC cell

Table 1 Parameters of the simulated circuit in EIS study

R_s (Ω)	CPE_1 ($\mu S s^{n_1}$)	n_1	R_p (Ω)	R_{ct} (Ω)	W_d ($\mu S s^{0.5}$)	CPE_2 ($\mu S s^{n_2}$)	n_2
49.0	13.7	0.81	31.8	91.9	90.7	208	0.9

is controlled by both EDL and pseudocapacitive mechanisms, which is also evidenced from the distorted rectangular shape of cyclic voltammograms in Fig. 8b.

The Bode plot is depicted in Fig. 8f displaying the variation of impedance and phase angle with frequency (f). From Fig. 8f, the real (C') and imaginary (C'') part of the specific capacitances were calculated using eqn (S5) and (S6).[†] The C' and C'' versus f plots are shown in Fig. S10a and b,[†] respectively. It is well-known that at the low frequency region the device shows capacitive behavior and high frequency region as a resistor.⁶⁶ It has been found that at the lower frequency region (0.1–10 Hz), both the C' and C'' increased with lowering the frequency. A highest C'' was found at the frequency of 0.1 Hz. From the imaginary part of specific capacitance, the time constant (τ_0), also known as dielectric relaxation time can be calculated using eqn (10).

$$\tau_0 = 1/f_0 \quad (10)$$

where, the f_0 represents the frequency at maximum imaginary capacitance.⁶⁷ The τ_0 was calculated to be 10 s when maximum capacitance is reached (Fig. S9[†]). In the phase plot, the phase angle reached to maximum of -68.9° at a low frequency of 0.79 Hz. It is well-known that a phase angle of -90° represents ideal capacitive behaviour, while a phase angle of -90° to -45° represents a primarily capacitive behavior and a phase angle of -45° to 0° represents mostly diffusion-controlled and resistive behavior of the electrode.⁶⁸ Here, the phase angle of -68.8° represents pseudocapacitive nature of the electrode as also evident from the CV study.⁶⁹

The Ragone chart which depicts the relationship between the energy density and power density attained by the SS-SC is plotted in Fig. 8g. An energy density of $0.20 \mu W h cm^{-2}$ was obtained at a power density of $16.26 \mu W cm^{-2}$. A comparison of energy and power densities of the inter-digital shaped $MoS_x@3D-PE$ SS-SC with some recently reported MoS_2 based SS-SCs which were fabricated either by 3D-printing or conventional processes are included in Table S1.[†] It was found that our synthesized SS-SC shows a comparable energy and power density with the 3D-printed SS-SCs reported in literature.

The cyclic stability was evaluated by repeating the GCD measurement for 10 000 cycles at the constant current density of $0.16 mA cm^{-2}$ as depicted in Fig. 8h. The SS-SC shows 100% of capacitance retention till 200 cycles and then a constant 90% of capacitance retention till ~ 3500 cycles. However, the capacitance retention dropped to 80% after 3500 cycles and remained constant till 9500 cycles. Nevertheless, the capacitance was increased to 90% of the initial capacitance after 9500 cycles. The initial decreasing trend of capacitance can be ascribed to the blocking of the electrode surface (pores and

channels) by the gel electrolyte. However, with the long run cyclic charge–discharge measurement in the PVA/ H_2SO_4 gel electrolyte, the partial dissolution of PLA in H_2SO_4 results in more accessible surface area which leads to an increasing trend after 9500 cycles. Only 10% of capacitance loss was observed after 10 000 cycles. This was also evidenced by our previous work with similar 3D-PE.⁷⁰

The combination of 3D-printing with the electrodeposition of active material can make any complex-shaped SC for modern electronics. A free-standing CEITEC-shaped SS-SC cell was prepared by assembling two identical CEITEC-shaped $MoS_x@3D-PE$ s as shown in Fig. S11a.[†] The electrochemical measurements including CV and GCD were performed for the CEITEC-shaped SS-SC cell as shown in Fig. S11b and c,[†] respectively. The CV and GCD patterns are in line with the interdigital-shaped SS-SC. The GCD study shows a capacitance of $3.64 mF cm^{-2}$ at a current density of $0.04 mA cm^{-2}$. Thus any complex shaped MoS_x coated free-standing SS-SC can be prepared as energy storage devices.

Conclusion

This study shows the integration of 3D-printing and electrodeposition techniques for facile and scalable fabrication of free-standing electrode for SC applications. The MoS_x , a promising material from transition metal chalcogenides family can be easily deposited at room temperature on the 3D-printed nanocarbon electrode. The MoS_x coating on the 3D-printed electrode increases the capacitive performance. The MoS_x coating shows both intercalative and pseudocapacitive charge storage mechanism. Solid-state supercapacitor cells can be fabricated with the modified electrode without the use of an external current collector and separator, which can provide promising capacitive performance. As a future outlook, other electrochemically active transition metal dichalcogenides can be electrodeposited on the 3D-printed nanocarbon electrode surface, and a supercapacitor cell with any desired shape can be made effortlessly according to the rising demand of modern electronics.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Acknowledgements

M.P. acknowledges the financial support by the Grant Agency of the Czech Republic (GACR EXPRO: 19-26896X), and K.G.

thanks to CEITEC Nano Research Infrastructure supported by MEYS CR (LM2018110) for providing spectroscopic and microscopic characterizations facilities and Marie Curie EU project 894457 – MotionEST. K.G. would like to thank Dr Christian Iffelsberger and Dr Siowwoon Ng for experimental help and reviewing the manuscript.

References

- S. Chu and A. Majumdar, *Nature*, 2012, **488**, 294–303.
- C. Liu, F. Li, L. P. Ma and H. M. Cheng, *Adv. Mater.*, 2010, **22**, E28–E62.
- X. Wang, X. Lu, B. Liu, D. Chen, Y. Tong and G. Shen, *Adv. Mater.*, 2014, **26**, 4763–4782.
- P. Simon and Y. Gogotsi, *Nat. Mater.*, 2008, **7**, 845–854.
- W. Zuo, R. Li, C. Zhou, Y. Li, J. Xia and J. Liu, *Adv. Sci.*, 2017, **4**, 1600539.
- G. Wang, L. Zhang and J. Zhang, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2012, **41**, 797–828.
- C. Zhu, T. Liu, F. Qian, W. Chen, S. Chandrasekaran, B. Yao, Y. Song, E. B. Duoss, J. D. Kuntz and C. M. Spadaccini, *Nano Today*, 2017, **15**, 107–120.
- F. Zhang, M. Wei, V. V. Viswanathan, B. Swart, Y. Shao, G. Wu and C. Zhou, *Nano Energy*, 2017, **40**, 418–431.
- K. Ghosh, C. Yue, M. Sk and R. Jena, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2017, **9**, 15350.
- K. Ghosh, C. Y. Yue, M. M. Sk, R. K. Jena and S. Bi, *Sustainable Energy Fuels*, 2018, **2**, 280–293.
- N. Singh, C. Galande, A. Miranda, A. Mathkar, W. Gao, A. L. M. Reddy, A. Vlad and P. M. Ajayan, *Sci. Rep.*, 2012, **2**, 481.
- M. Wei, F. Zhang, W. Wang, P. Alexandridis, C. Zhou and G. Wu, *J. Power Sources*, 2017, **354**, 134–147.
- M. Areir, Y. Xu, D. Harrison and J. Fyson, *Mater. Sci. Eng., B*, 2017, **226**, 29–38.
- C. W. Foster, M. P. Down, Y. Zhang, X. Ji, S. J. Rowley-Neale, G. C. Smith, P. J. Kelly and C. E. Banks, *Sci. Rep.*, 2017, **7**, 42233.
- K. Fu, Y. Yao, J. Dai and L. Hu, *Adv. Mater.*, 2017, **29**, 1603486.
- Z. Qiangqiang, Z. Feng, M. S. Pradeep, L. Hui, Z. Chi and L. Dong, *Small*, 2016, **12**, 1702–1708.
- M. P. Browne, E. Redondo and M. Pumera, *Chem. Rev.*, 2020, **120**, 2783–2810.
- C. Iffelsberger, S. Ng and M. Pumera, *Appl. Mater. Today*, 2020, **20**, 100654.
- M. P. Browne, F. Novotný, Z. k. Sofer and M. Pumera, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2018, **10**, 40294–40301.
- Q4** C. L. Manzanares Palenzuela, F. Novotný, P. Krupička, Z. k. Sofer and M. Pumera, *Anal. Chem.*, 2018, **90**, 5753–5757.
- R. Gusmão, M. P. Browne, Z. Sofer and M. Pumera, *Electrochem. Commun.*, 2019, **102**, 83–88.
- F. Novotný, V. Urbanová, J. Plutnar and M. Pumera, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2019, **11**, 35371–35375.
- M. P. Browne, V. Urbanova, J. Plutnar, F. Novotný and M. Pumera, *J. Mater. Chem. A*, 2020, **8**, 7.
- M. P. Browne and M. Pumera, *Chem. Commun.*, 2019, **55**, 8374–8377.
- C. L. Manzanares-Palenzuela, S. Hermanova, Z. Sofer and M. Pumera, *Nanoscale*, 2019, **11**, 12124–12131.
- S. Ng, C. Iffelsberger, Z. Sofer and M. Pumera, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, 2020, 1910193.
- C. Y. Foo, H. N. Lim, M. A. Mahdi, M. H. Wahid and N. M. Huang, *Sci. Rep.*, 2018, **8**, 1–11.
- M. Saraf, K. Natarajan and S. M. Mobin, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2018, **10**, 16588–16595.
- C. Zhou, J. Wang, X. Yan, X. Yuan, D. Wang, Y. Zhu and X. Cheng, *Ceram. Int.*, 2019, **45**, 21534–21543.
- L. Cao, S. Yang, W. Gao, Z. Liu, Y. Gong, L. Ma, G. Shi, S. Lei, Y. Zhang and S. Zhang, *Small*, 2013, **9**, 2905–2910.
- A. Yan, J. Velasco Jr., S. Kahn, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, F. Wang, M. F. Crommie and A. Zettl, *Nano Lett.*, 2015, **15**, 6324–6331.
- Y. H. Lee, X. Q. Zhang, W. Zhang, M. T. Chang, C. T. Lin, K. D. Chang, Y. C. Yu, J. T. W. Wang, C. S. Chang and L. J. Li, *Adv. Mater.*, 2012, **24**, 2320–2325.
- Y. Peng, Z. Meng, C. Zhong, J. Lu, W. Yu, Y. Jia and Y. Qian, *Chem. Lett.*, 2001, **30**, 772–773.
- D. Kong, H. Wang, J. J. Cha, M. Pasta, K. J. Koski, J. Yao and Y. Cui, *Nano Lett.*, 2013, **13**, 1341–1347.
- J. N. Coleman, M. Lotya, A. O'Neill, S. D. Bergin, P. J. King, U. Khan, K. Young, A. Gaucher, S. De and R. J. Smith, *Science*, 2011, **331**, 568–571.
- R. J. Smith, P. J. King, M. Lotya, C. Wirtz, U. Khan, S. De, A. O'Neill, G. S. Duesberg, J. C. Grunlan and G. Moriarty, *Adv. Mater.*, 2011, **23**, 3944–3948.
- C. Rao and A. Nag, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2010, **2010**, 4244–4250.
- H. Ramakrishna Matte, A. Gomathi, A. K. Manna, D. J. Late, R. Datta, S. K. Pati and C. Rao, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2010, **49**, 4059–4062.
- B. D. Falola, T. Wiltowski and I. I. Suni, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 2016, **163**, D568.
- E. Ponomarev, M. Neumann-Spallart, G. Hodes and C. Lévy-Clément, *Thin Solid Films*, 1996, **280**, 86–89.
- A. Albu-Yaron, C. Lévy-Clément, A. Katty, S. Bastide and R. Tenne, *Thin Solid Films*, 2000, **361**, 223–228.
- A. Ambrosi and M. Pumera, *ACS Catal.*, 2016, **6**, 3985–3993.
- Z. S. Wu, A. Winter, L. Chen, Y. Sun, A. Turchanin, X. Feng and K. Müllen, *Adv. Mater.*, 2012, **24**, 5130–5135.
- H. W. Wang, P. Skeldon and G. E. Thompson, *Surf. Coat. Technol.*, 1997, **91**, 200–207.
- T. Wang, J. Zhuo, K. Du, B. Chen, Z. Zhu, Y. Shao and M. Li, *Adv. Mater.*, 2014, **26**, 3761–3766.
- D. Belanger, G. Laperrière and B. Marsan, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1993, **347**, 165–183.
- D. Belanger, G. Laperrière, F. Girard, D. Guay and G. Tourillon, *Chem. Mater.*, 1993, **5**, 861–868.
- M. Kalani and R. Yunus, *Int. J. Nanomed.*, 2012, **7**, 2165.

- 1 49 F. T. Johra, J.-W. Lee and W.-G. Jung, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 2014, **20**, 2883–2887.
- 50 A. Cao, C. Xu, J. Liang, D. Wu and B. Wei, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2001, **344**, 13–17.
- 5 51 W. Zhang, Y. He, M. Zhang, Z. Yin and Q. Chen, *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.*, 2000, **33**, 912.
- 52 T. Mazza, E. Barborini, P. Piseri, P. Milani, D. Cattaneo, A. L. Bassi, C. E. Bottani and C. Ducati, *Phys. Rev. B: Condens. Matter Mater. Phys.*, 2007, **75**, 045416.
- 10 53 K. Ghosh, S. Ng, C. Iffelsberger and M. Pumera, *Chem. – Eur. J.*, 2020, **26**, 15746–15753.
- 54 A. C. Ferrari and D. M. Basko, *Nat. Nanotechnol.*, 2013, **8**, 235–246.
- 15 55 S. S. Nardekar, K. Krishnamoorthy, P. Pazhamalai, S. Sahoo, V. K. Mariappan and S.-J. Kim, *J. Mater. Chem. A*, 2020.
- Q6** 56 B. Zhang, X. Ji, K. Xu, C. Chen, X. Xiong, J. Xiong, Y. Yao, L. Miao and J. Jiang, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2016, **217**, 1–8.
- 20 57 V. Augustyn, J. Come, M. A. Lowe, J. W. Kim, P.-L. Taberna, S. H. Tolbert, H. D. Abruña, P. Simon and B. Dunn, *Nat. Mater.*, 2013, **12**, 518–522.
- 58 R. Wang, S. Wang, X. Peng, Y. Zhang, D. Jin, P. K. Chu and L. Zhang, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2017, **9**, 32745–32755.
- 59 Z. Le, F. Liu, P. Nie, X. Li, X. Liu, Z. Bian, G. Chen, H. B. Wu and Y. Lu, *ACS Nano*, 2017, **11**, 2952–2960.
- 60 T. Brezesinski, J. Wang, S. H. Tolbert and B. Dunn, *Nat. Mater.*, 2010, **9**, 146–151.
- 61 Y. Jiang and J. Liu, *Energy Environ. Mater.*, 2019, **2**, 30–37.
- 62 S. Ahn, Y. Choi, J. Kim and J. Han, *Surf. Coat. Technol.*, 2002, **150**, 319–326.
- 63 S. Ahn, J. Lee, H. Kim and J. Kim, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, 2004, **233**, 105–114.
- 64 K. Ghosh and C. Y. Yue, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2018, **276**, 47–63.
- 65 J. Liu, J. Essner and J. Li, *Chem. Mater.*, 2010, **22**, 5022–5030.
- 66 F. Barzegar, A. A. Khaleed, F. U. Ugbo, K. O. Oyeniran, D. Y. Momodu, A. Bello, J. K. Dangbegnon and N. Manyala, *AIP Adv.*, 2016, **6**, 115306.
- 67 P. Taberna, P. Simon and J.-F. Fauvarque, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 2003, **150**, A292.
- 68 C. J. Raj, M. Rajesh, R. Manikandan, J. Y. Sim, K. H. Yu, S. Y. Park, J. H. Song and B. C. Kim, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2017, **247**, 949–957.
- 69 S. Senthilkumar, R. K. Selvan, N. Ponpandian and J. Melo, *RSC Adv.*, 2012, **2**, 8937–8940.
- 70 E. Redondo, S. Ng, J. Muñoz and M. Pumera, *Nanoscale*, 2020, **12**, 19673–19680.
- 1 5
- 10 15
- 20 25
- 30 35
- 40 45
- 50 55